
METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the author provides information about the methodology of teaching foreign languages in preschool education including English. Furthermore, we can observe different methods of teaching English language in foreign countries and their tactics to apply it in practice.

Keywords: *Preschool education, methodology, method, English language, "Game" method, "Doman" method, "Communicative" method.*

Preschool educational organizations today are increasingly striving to support the development of individual abilities of the child, to prepare him so that he can meet the modern requirements of a dynamically developing world. Despite the fact that the issue of teaching a foreign language to preschool children is still the subject of extensive discussions, this topic firmly occupies its niche in children's educational organizations, development centers, and in the programs of preparatory school courses. There is a new international approach to primary language education and foreign language proficiency is one of the most important competencies of a modern person [3].

In this regard, we would like to note that the role of English language as a foreign language is growing day by day. People immigrate to different countries to work or just live in. And they immigrate with their family. And they have an interest in teaching their child, of course, English language. Considering that factor, we want to share the methods of teaching English as a foreign language.

English is the language of science, computers, diplomacy, and tourism. English is the official language of 53 countries and is used as a lingua franca (a mutually known language) by people from all around the world. This means that whether you’re working in Tokyo, or travelling in Italy, studying English can help you have a conversation with people from all over the world.

If we focus at language learning; it is difficult for a child to learn the language at preschool age. Because they still don't know the purpose of learning the language. In order for the child to be interested, the teacher must have an interest and methods for teaching young children. For example, make cardboard plates with each letter of the alphabet, and write words to them, and there should be a picture in the background indicating the meaning of the word. This method is also called the "Doman" method.

In no case should you force a child to teach. If lessons become a duty, then they can quickly get bored, and subsequently it may be difficult for the baby to learn the language. The main task of parents and teachers is to arouse interest in the language, and the game helps well in this. Through the game, children learn about the world and are easily involved in the process, easily mastering important language skills. According to A.V. Konyshева, it makes the educational process more meaningful and of higher quality, since:

- the game draws each student individually and all together into active cognitive activity and, thus, is an effective means of managing the educational process;
- learning in the game is carried out through the students' own activities, which have the character of a special type of practice, during which up to 90% of the information is assimilated;
- the game is a free activity that gives the opportunity for choice, self-expression, self-determination and self-development for its participants;
- the game has a certain result and stimulates the student to achieve the goal (victory) and awareness of the way to achieve the goal;
- in the game, teams or individual students are initially equal (there are no bad and good students: there are only players); the result depends on the player himself, his level of preparedness, abilities, endurance, skills, character;
- the impersonal learning process in the game acquires personal significance;
- competitiveness — an integral part of the game — is attractive to students; the pleasure gained from the game creates a comfortable state in foreign language lessons and increases the desire to study the subject;
- there is always a mystery in the game, an incomplete answer, which activates the student's mental activity, pushes him to search for an answer [1].

In addition to determining the role of games in the educational process, it is important to know their varieties. S.V. Kulnevich and T.P. Lakotsenina offer the following classification of games:

Exercise games. They usually take 10-15 minutes and are aimed at improving the cognitive abilities of students, are a good means for the development of cognitive interests, comprehension and consolidation of educational material, its application in new situations. These are a variety of quizzes, crosswords, puzzles, chain words, charades and puzzles, explanations of proverbs and sayings, riddles.

Travel games. They can be conducted both directly in the classroom and during extracurricular activities. They serve mainly the purposes of deepening, comprehension and consolidation of educational material. The activation of students in travel games is expressed in oral stories, questions, answers, in their personal experiences and judgments.

A story (role-playing) game differs from exercise games and travel games in that the conditions of an imaginary situation are staged, and students play certain roles.

The competition game may include all the above-mentioned types of didactic games or their individual elements. To conduct this type of game, students are divided into groups, teams, between which there is a competition. An essential feature of the competition game is the presence of competitive struggle and cooperation in it [2].

One more method of studying English language can be noted. This is to show the child cartoons that they love to watch in their native language, in English. Every child has an interest in cartoons. We think this is a useful method. This method will also help the child to master emotions, facial expressions, the use of words and other factors of English language.

Another method is the communicative method. This method is almost used in all school and preschool education. Language in the communicative methodology is considered as a method and means of communication, therefore the best way to learn a language is the process of communication. The goal in learning any foreign language is always the ability to use language as a means of expressing one's thoughts and intentions and to exchange them in various situations in the process of interaction with other communication participants.

For the primary school or preschool level, there are the following goals in learning English language using a communicative method:

- to promote the familiarization of children with a new language world, when children do not yet experience psychological barriers in using a foreign language as a means of communication;

- to develop children's readiness to communicate in a foreign language and a positive attitude to its further study;
- develop basic communication skills in four types of speech activity (speaking, listening, reading, writing), taking into account the speech capabilities and needs of younger students;
- to acquaint younger schoolchildren with the world of foreign peers, with foreign songs, poetic and fairy-tale folklore, samples of children's fiction available to children in the foreign language being studied;

The most important principle of the communicative methodology is that the learning process should be interesting and exciting. Such topics and activities are selected for classes that cause a desire to communicate and learn more.

Pros and cons of teaching kids a foreign language;

Today's parents are increasingly trying to start the process of educating their children as early as possible: they bring kids to early development centers, sign up for additional classes or study at home, considering it useful for the further development of the child. At the same time, teaching a foreign language is among the three most popular directions.

Indeed, teachers believe that early learning of a foreign language carries many advantages:

- provides new sources of information about the surrounding world;
- promotes the development of communication skills;
- develops logical and spatial thinking;
- gives a broader concept of phonemic diversity;
- facilitates learning other subjects in the future;
- trains memory.

But do not forget about the pitfalls. It is very easy to overload a child at preschool age with information, which will affect not only the effectiveness of classes, but also further motivation. You also need to make sure that the baby does not replace the concepts of one language with another. And of course, it is important that the baby learns the correct pronunciation, and for this it will be an excellent solution to learn "firsthand" [5].

At the end of the article, it can be noted that English is a difficult and at the same time a very rich and interesting language. When teaching a language, the teacher must first of all love and respect this language. And must have knowledge of teaching methods and be able to use them.

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